

EFFECTIVENESS OF COLLABORATIVE, COMMUNITY AND CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN TERMS OF ACHIEVEMENT AT +2 LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

The present research study entitled- EFFECTIVENESS OF COLLABORATIVE, COMMUNITY AND CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN TERMS OF ACHIEVEMENT AT +2 LEVEL belongs to the area of educational management and educational technology. This project based on teaching learning model is strongly rooted to constructivism. In this teaching learning model both teacher and students engages themselves and immerse into a sequential scenarios, where the outcome is pre-determined. Both Teacher and Student have to master the situation at hand. The Teacher with more experience and knowledge reflects perfectly on the complex situations on the Teacher's side. The study revealed that C3MS model significantly affects achievement of the students.

Keywords:

Collaborative, Community, Content Management, Educational Technology.

INTRODUCTION

The modern classroom has gone way beyond simple textbooks and chalkboards when it comes to finding ways to engage with pupils. Technology has opened up many more methods for helping children learn on many different levels, from using computers in the classroom to enjoying the benefits of the internet. There are numerous ways that teachers can use technology in the Classroom and many are already doing it. Some modern classroom started using Interactive Smart Boards in place of traditional chalk or white boards. One of the models which are based on the assumption of constructivism is C3MS model.

The term C3MS refers to collaborative, community, and content management system. This teaching model has strong links to constructivism. From the constructivist point of view learning is considered as an active process in which pupil construct their knowledge by relating it to their previous experiences in complex and real situations in life.

This model requires a special two – way communication structure, the communication is on equal terms. Teacher and learner work together to master problems. The environment is constructed in a way that it represents at least in certain aspects reality or it is reality constrained by certain variables. There is a two way communication on equal terms, using either linguistics representation or other adequate kinds of languages. In that respect it is by no means objective knowledge but personal knowledge.

RATIONALE

Large number of researches is conducted and various teaching and learning strategies are proposed to answer the question, "How can we teach more effectively?" The C3MS is an attempt which favors "Constructivism based" teaching/ learning which satisfy the basic assumptions of La. Merrill instructional theory. The researchers conducted in the field of C3MS model are very less in number. Although researches are conducted in the field of various components of C3MS model separately. So, there is a wide gap in the researches in this area.

As in emerging society only one method of teaching is not sufficient to fulfill the multifaceted objectives of education. The integrated C3MS model is an attempt where student learn to develop, organize and retrieve the knowledge in proper manner.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

EFFECTIVENESS OF COLLABORATIVE, COMMUNITY AND CONTENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN TERMS OF ACHIEVEMENT AT +2 LEVEL

OBJECTIVE

To compare the adjusted mean achievement scores of the students studying through C3MS model with those studying through traditional method by taking pre-achievement score as covariate.

HYPOTHESIS

There will be no significant difference between the adjusted mean achievement scores of students belonging to experimental group with that of control group by considering pre-achievement scores as covariate.

METHODOLOGY

SAMPLE

The present study was experimental in nature and was conducted in two schools. All the students were studying in class XI. Two schools were selected using Random Sampling Technique. The randomly selected schools were Maharishi Vidya Mandir and Lokmanya Vidya Niketan.

DESIGN

The present study was experimental in nature. The design of the study is posttest only control group design. The treatment was assigned randomly to the selected two groups. The group who received Treatment of C₃MS was the experimental group while the second group taught through conventional method was the Control group. After this both the groups were pre- tested using the test of Achievement of Chemistry topics viz: Environmental Chemistry, States of Matter, Chemical Bonding, Chemical families and Hydrogen developed by the investigator.

TOOLS

In the present study, the data was collected through the achievement developed by the investigator.

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The interpretation and results are as follows:

To compare the adjusted mean achievement scores of the students studying through C3MS model with those studying through traditional method by taking pre-achievement score as covariate.

The first objective was to compare adjusted mean achievement scores of the students studying through C3MS model with those studying through traditional method by taking pre-achievement score as covariate. The data related to this objective were analyzed with help Analysis of Covariance. The result is given in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: Summary of ANCOVA of overall achievement scores of students studying through C3MS model with those studying through traditional method by taking overall pre-achievement score as covariate.

Source	Type III Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F
Treatment	2227.232	1	2227.232	142.575**
Error	1140.370	73	15.622	
Total	3664.039	75		

Significant at 0.01 level

From table 1.1 it can be seen that the adjusted F-value for the overall achievement is 142.575. Which is significant at 0.01 level with df 1/73. It indicates that the adjusted mean achievement scores of the students studying through C3MS model with those studying through traditional method differ significantly when pre-achievement score was considered as covariate. Thus, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in scores of the mean adjusted mean achievement scores of the students studying through C3MS model with those studying through traditional method by taking pre-achievement score as covariate is rejected.

FINDING

C3MS Model was found to be significantly more effective than traditional method in terms of achievement when groups were matched with respect to the pre achievement scores.

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